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Research Article

**ROLE OF HEALTH EDUCATION AND ENVIRONMENTAL
MEDICAL ISSUES IN ELECTORAL PROCESS IN PAKISTAN****Dr. Maria Ishtiaq, Dr. Minahil shaukat, Dr. Anam ijaz**
Avicenna Medical College and Hospital, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: Research was held for the evaluation of wheatear health education and other environmental medical and social issues influence the electoral process in Pakistan.

Study design: _Exploratory quantitative and case study method.

Place & duration of study: Present research paper was completed in the period of June 2017 to Feb 2018 and the place was NA-126 Lahore.

Material and method: In this research content analysis done. This research was held to compare the healthy educated people of Lahore wheatear health and education effect electoral process in Lahore NA-126 as compared to other areas of Lahore and political influences on housing and other medical and social issues of people after political selection.

Result: Health and education greatly influence electoral process in Pakistan.

Conclusion: Research shows that healthier and well educated you are the more likely you are to cast a vote. Social connection is really an important factor as we have to decide where we are going as a country morally, economically and politically.

Key words: Health, education, environmental medical and social issues.

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INTRODUCTION:

The word Health Education is a broad term. Its implications are manifold. If at one side, it means the formal learning process in some institution like school, college or university; then at the other, it implies the lifelong process of acquiring knowledge through informal means like society, environment or surroundings. Both orientate people in their own right. Educated and healthy mind is obviously a relative and subjective terminology. Formal education does not give any guarantee of producing a learned mind. Even an illiterate person can be more learned than an educated one, as Francis Bacon once said that the real wisdom lies with the commoner. So I would try to chalk out a criterion which would be, to an extent, acceptable to all as it be per international standards. My research seeks to gauge education in reference to electoral politics, so its definition would naturally be in accordance with that. It is not an easy task to determine in black and white what an educated mind in reference to electoral politics is. However, I would deem the education taken up to the age of adult franchise as a yardstick to measure the impact of education on electoral politics in Lahore. Adult franchise implies that anyone who is above the age of 18 is qualified for voting. Though the age of voting differs in different countries but overwhelming majority of the world states, including Pakistan, grants the right of vote at 18. In Pakistani education system, students normally attain Higher Secondary or 12 years education up till the age of 18. So I would consider my respondents "educated" if they at least have obtained education to the Intermediate level.

Giving a brief introduction to education, I would now move to the second part of my research which is electoral politics. Electoral politics is the process of selection of a person or persons from numerous candidates for a political office. Electoral politics is the backbone of democracy, which is the most famous and successful political system of the modern world. It is necessary, though not the only condition of democracy. It is so important because 'popular choice' is a tool in hands of masses to have an indirect control over government. Fair electoral process leads to establish true democracy which in turns builds the socio-political and economic structures of the state. Through electoral process we can realize the all-important concepts of democracy like 'popular control' and 'political equality'; prior implies the control of masses on decision making process and latter one enfold the respect and equality of masses in policy making. This process realizes the dream of indirect participation of public

by delegating their powers to a set or group of public officials. By the voting system, composition of parliament is ordained. Electoral process covers wide range of rules, for example, "ease of access to the ballot for would-be candidates, the right to vote, the fairness of the administration of the election, the transparency of the counting of votes---all are very important in determining the significance and legitimacy of an election."(Callagher and Mitchell, 2005). Electoral process lays deep impacts on other things as well, for instance; it may profoundly change the shape of party system; determines whether there would be a coalition government or a single party regime; in holding representatives accountable; and ultimately shaping the quality of government.

Existing theories determine that electoral politics, health and education have mutual influences. Many a theories establish relationship between them. Existences of both have political consequences on each other. Some suggest a direct relationship, i.e. increase in educational level leads to an active and vibrant electoral system. Conversely, some studies draw on the contrary conclusion that education, particularly in third world, leads to a passive political culture. People, as they keep getting highly educated, alienate themselves from practical or electoral politics. One of aims of my research would be gauging the influence of education on voters in Lahore; whether education is leading to a coherent participant culture or it is on the contrary.

Pakistan has never been up to the international standards of western democracy. It has always been vacillating between praetorian rule and sham democracy. First general elections of Pakistan were held after 23 years of its inception. Though people exercised their right of vote many a times during this time period but that did not contribute anything worth mentioning to the political system. According to Report of the electoral reform Commission Karachi 1956 Elections held in 1950s were even deemed as 'farce, a mockery and fraud upon the electorate by many observers and analyst. Things further deteriorated in approaching decades due to intermittent Martial Laws. So much so it is said that not even single elections ever held in Pakistan had been fair and free. Resultantly, people belonging to upper and upper middle class distanced themselves from politics. It should also be kept in notice that these two classes belong to high literacy and SERL (Socio Economic Resource Level) in Pakistan. But as these groups have frequent access to electronic media and press, so they are quite well versed with ongoing political developments. Consequently they engage

themselves in political discussions and debates but remain aloof of practical politics. They are generally found to be engaged in passive participatory activities rather than proactive ones. It is said to be one of the reason that voter turn out has always been very low and non representative governments have been formed all along. People who did not vote were also generally termed as “silent majority.” But elections of May 2013 were an exception when voter turn out was about 55 % and a party emerged as single largest party at federal level. An unprecedented number of 15 million (approx) votes were cast in the said elections. I would make a case study of one constituency, which is NA-126, of Lahore and try to determine that how much education has affected or contributed in making people participate in practical politics. There are a number of reasons for selecting this constituency; high literacy rate and different voting pattern are the leading factors among all others.

Objectives of the study

- To comprehend the ongoing electoral trends in Lahore.
- To gauge whether education and health lays any impact on minds of the voter or not.
- To measure whether different voting trend in NA-126 from rest of Lahore was result of educated voters or not.
- To asses the importance of education in reference to politics in eyes of the voters
- To explore the myth of social determinants of voting.
- To know the opinion of people about transparency of previous elections.
- To judge the political mobilization and awareness of people.

Scope and significance of the study

Scope of this study is high because it pertains to one of the most important aspects of society. Electoral politics is the connection which interlinks the demands of the people to policy making by political elite, hence its importance can not be negated. Particularly after the restoration and continuity of

democracy in our country, the demand of fair and free use of right of voting has been increased manifold. Democracy in the Third World is generally associated with pejorative terms like ‘sham democracy’, ‘pseudo democracy’, ‘feudalistic democracy’ or ‘illiberal democracy’; and its voters are alleged of voting candidates on social determinants like cast, creed, race, ethnicity or clan (*biradri*). But in the previous elections, Pakistani voter has refuted this theory when virtually a new party, named Pakistan Tehreek.e.Insaf (PTI), emerged out of nothing and turned into second largest party if we take popular vote as criterion. In all the four provinces, this party secured stunning amount of votes and these votes were definitely cast beyond any provincial, ethnic, religious or racial determinant. Most of the analysts opine that the silent educated majority brought this change. It was frequently observed during the election campaign that such a class was mobilized this time which always remained aloof of the politics. So much so that PTI secured seats in strongholds of other parties, including in two provincial capitals, and grasped a sweeping victory in the third province. This soft change is said to be owed to educated middle and rich class who remained detached of politics. This study would ferret out the magnitude of reality in this notion. It would not only be helpful in determining the fact but also be a benchmark study for forthcoming researchers.

Research Questions

1. Is health and education the reason behind high voter turnout and different voting trend from rest of Lahore in NA-126?
2. To what extent politics of patronage is important in politics of Lahore?
3. What is the veracity behind the myth of social determinants of voting?
4. Does educational level boost political mobilization?
5. Do people think previous elections were transparent?
6. Are other environmental medical issues affect electoral politics or social economic behavior of people towards politics?

Conceptual framework

In conceptual framework of my research, I have broadly categorized four variables which are Electoral Politics, Educational Variables, Demographic Variables and lastly Politics of Patronage. Dependent variable in my research is electoral politics. Dependent variable is the key variable and centre of research of any study. Main investigation is done on it and it responds independent variable.

Independent variable influences dependent variable in a positive or negative manner. This variable is the *cause* of the *effect*. I have divided independent variables broadly into two categories in my conceptual framework. One is the Educational Variables, and the other is Demographic Variables. Educational variables are further divided into level of education, academic performance, and family's educational background, mode of education and medium of education. Demographic variables have been divided into age, sex, geographic background, ethnic background, sectarian background, cast and profession. All these factors lay profound affects on electoral politics. These elements orientate people politically in their own right, hence impact electoral politics. As we know that dependent variable is also

present if independent variable is present; and in case of increase in independent variable there can be an increase or decrease in dependent variable.

Politics of Patronage serves as Intervening Variable in the conceptual framework. Patronage in politics implies "the control of or power to make appointments to government jobs or the power to grant other political favors." This variable, as studies are cited further in literature review, is of critical importance in politics of Pakistan in general. As we are aware that intervening variable intervenes the time independent variable begins operating to impact the dependent variable. So implementing this thing here, when educational and demographic variables affect electoral politics, politics of patronage comes at surface and lays profound impacts upon independent variables, and ultimately the dependent variable.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

In my research work, I would use Exploratory, Quantitative and Case-Study method. "Exploratory research is a methodological approach that is primarily concerned with discovery and with generating and building theory. In the social sciences

exploratory research is wedded to the notion of exploration and researcher as explorer.”(Jupp, 2006) This kind of research is most suitable to the related topic.

After the use of Exploratory Research, Quantitative method of research would be applied. Quantitative relationship between the variables pertaining to the research would be measured. Keeping the nature of the research in mind, Questionnaire would be used for collection of data.

Further Case Study method will be used, to study the factors and variables of a specific area of interest and its impact on other variables jointly. Case Study would be done in constituency number NA-126 of Lahore. There are quite a number of reasons for selecting this constituency. First of all, Lahore is one of the most urbanized area of the Punjab and Pakistan as well. Political analysts believe that change always come from urban areas and then its trickle down affect strikes the other areas. Lahore has always been the epicenter of political activities of Pakistan. Politics of Lahore affects entire Punjab and who holds the Punjab rule Pakistan. All the important political movements which toppled down governments in history of Pakistan, originated from Lahore. Due to its critical importance, Lahore is often referred as “Takht.e.Lahore”, though pejoratively. In the previous elections, again a change has come from Lahore and Pakistan Tehree.k.e.Insaf won a seat of national assembly and two of provincial assembly in centre of Lahore. This constituency has been a stronghold of Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz. This different voting pattern tempted me to select this constituency in order to figure out the determinants of a changed voting pattern.

As it is well known that sampling is of critical importance, particularly in primary research. No researcher can study entire population, hence a representative sample is drawn from the population through process of sampling. It “is the process of selecting a sufficient number of elements from the population, so that a study of the sample and an understanding of its properties or characteristics would make it possible for us to generalize such properties or characteristics to the population elements.” (Sekaram, 2003) To select a proper representative sample through suitable sampling method is probably the most crucial step in research.

After contemplating over the sampling method, I have decided to adopt Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling. In this method, “once the population has been stratified in some meaningful

way, a sample of members from each stratum can be drawn using either a simple random sampling or a systematic sampling procedure. The subjects drawn from each stratum can be either proportionate or disproportionate to the number of elements in the stratum.” (Sekaram, 2003) NA-126 is a big constituency of Lahore, details of which would be discussed latter, which has 359492 registered voters. It has two provincial assembly seats which are PP-151 and 152. The whole constituency has been divided into fourteen sub-administrative units called as Union Councils (UC). These Union Councils are UC number 95, 97, 98, 99, 102, 103, 104, 108, 109, 116, 126, 127, 128 and 132. Voters Lists of each Union Council is available at UC Office. After getting access to the UC Offices, first two and last two voters of male voters list and first two and last two voters of female voters list of each Union Council would be added to the sample. In this way eight voters from each Union Council would be added to the sample; making a sample of one hundred and twelve.

Literature Review

The Pakistan Voter: Electoral Politics and Voting Behavior in the Punjab is a comprehensive study of voting behavior of people in Pakistan generally and in the Punjab particularly. It is written by Andrew Roberts Wilder. The writer has used empirical method to collect data. He starts his study by raising the question ‘who is voting for whom and why?’ In the initial two chapters he gives a brief historical review of elections reviews the relevant literature. In the next chapter he makes an analysis of electoral geography of the Punjab and divides the Punjab into five zones, i.e., central, northern, western and southern. According to him, central zone is most crucial when it comes to the electoral politics. Since the inception of Peoples Party, rural areas (feudal class) are prone to this party which had alienated urban middle class, which stands against this party in electoral politics. Fifth chapter has been specifically written on electoral psychology of Lahore, where Peoples Party had strong candidates since 1970; but later on voting pattern changed and politically unknown candidates of Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz started winning, leading the writer to the conclusion that party loyalty or affiliation became the order of the day instead of strong candidates. An interesting finding of the writer is he demolishes the social determinant of voting, even *biradri*. Voting preferences are different for men and women, young and old and the myth of one male member determining to whom the family will vote is completely false. Though, he finds out that *patronage* is the most important factor of electorate attraction.

With the passage of time, influence of religious political parties have abated, but they can not be neglected altogether, however, 'Islamic parties suffer from the same electoral problem that nearly third parties have with a 'first-past-the-post' electoral system.' (Wilder, 1999)

Another pertinent reading is *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* by Paulo Freire. Though this book has nothing directly to do with electoral politics but it is quite relevant to my proposed topic of research. Paulo has criticized the western education system on account of teacher-student relationship. According to him, the teacher is a learned and experienced 'subject'; whereas a student is an object which 'filled' by teacher's omniscience. In this methodology, reality becomes static and students 'detach' themselves from it. Such a milieu hampers change, creativity, inquiry and alienates students from reality. Due to lack of analysis, the knowledge gained is virtually of no use. He terms such type of education as "banking concept of education." (Friere, 2000) This system, the writer believes creates master-slave relationship which inculcates oppressive inclinations in students. These students when inducted in society are nothing more than extension of cause of dominant elite. In my study, I would be typically interested in knowing whether traditional educational system is really a tool of oppression when it comes to the politics, or it is a liberating element.

Democratization in Pakistan: A Case Study of 2002 Election is a book written by a well known writer and Professor of Lahore University of Management Sciences, Muhammad Waseem. This book is about the process of democratization taken place under Pervez Musharraf's praetorian rule. This book is trifurcated into pre-election constitutional, political and institutional changes; dynamics of 2002 general election, state power used on political parties and campaigning; and process of formation of central and provincial governments in the post election era. The writer has analyzed the electoral process in terms of transition of power from military to civil government. (Waseem, 2006)

Electoral Systems: A Comparative Introduction by David M. Farrell is a work on electoral reforms. The writer explains why certain political actors stand for status quo and other are tilted towards change. This work may help those in deciding to take sides if they are undecided or neutral. It can also help in changing one's mind in case he has taken decision. In the second edition of the book, the writer has comprehensively explained the dynamics and

structure of electoral rules. Though this work revolves around the political systems of the West but the narratives explained in the book can be generalized to all other systems as well.

Farrell "argues that electoral systems must be classified either by their outputs or by their mechanics... While the output of an electoral system can be either proportional or non-proportional, the mechanics depend on three elements: the district magnitude, the electoral formula and the ballot structure." (Farrel, 2011) It makes readers easy to comprehend complex electoral systems unlike other writers who take too many variables in explaining systems, resulting in confusion for the readers.

In the earlier part of the book, Farrell identifies outputs of the electoral systems and their relationship nature with mechanic elements. For instance, in the 2nd chapter, the writer throws light on science of Single Member Plurality System (SPM) and explains how it works in relevance to size of the constituency; how votes are converted into seats through formula and structure of the ballot.

In the latter part of the book, Farrell approaches electoral systems analytically. He reviews literature on strategic and systematic aspect of political systems. By inferring the relationship between disproportional electoral process and representation of voters, he poses question whether representation systems are contributing in corroborating or weakening representative institutions. This is a major criticism which can help determining us that which is more close to democratic representation, Proportional Representation or Single Member Plurality System.

Farrell's work has opened new era of discussions system of electoral design. He successfully deduces that in what ways electoral arrangements affects political behavior.

College Students and Politics: A Literature Review is a working paper issued by Centre for Information and Research on Civil Learning and Engagement (CIRCLE) in May 2006. This research paper is a continuation of "College Students Talk Politics" published in 1993. It was too a research work done in order to comprehend the interest of college students in political affair. The report studied focus group of students on campuses of universities and found out that most of the students had negative connotations about politics. They were of the opinion that politics does not solve problems rather proves counterproductive in solving matters. Since this study, numerous other studies have been carried out

on the same issue, among them, according civic mansion research organization “Civic Mission of Schools 2003”, “Keeter et al. 2002” and “National Commission on Civic Renewal 1998” are worth mentioning. These studies pinpointed that one of the greatest dangers to democracy is that politics is turning out to be an agent of relegating youth from the mainstream. Under the aforementioned background this research paper was written. Like the previous studies, focus groups of students were formed at university campuses, but sample was collected by keeping in view the knowledge, skills, values, practices and attitudes of students regarding students. Detailed study showed that students of universities were still apathetic to political participation but the silver lining is that after a constants decline there has been a rise in trust in government; increase in voting ration and in some other forms of political participation. Besides this, there has been a rise in involvement of youngsters in societal affairs and community building, which, along with the political participation, has been referred by Nelscon media report 2006 “scissor effect” in the research paper. This rise has a significance impact on democracy. Though people believe that there is a big difference in political participation and community service, but it goes without saying that it is an alternative politics. It is “politics that is not called politics.” In the end of the article it is recognized that there is a huge political potential in youth studying at university campuses but that is needed to be rectified properly in favor of fostering democracy.

How local media coverage of elections can help turn out more and better informed voters is an article of Hilary A. Niles, a multimedia investigative storyteller. The writer believes that studies have shown a clear co relation between voter turn out and media consumption. Literature of the article is based on the assumption that media coverage enhances knowledge of general public on political issues and ultimately affects the decision making pattern of people. This assumption was made after conducting a survey after the presidential debate of George W. Bush and John Kerry held on television.

After the emergence of internet as the most powerful tool, importance of other sources like radio, newspaper and magazines have eroded. So much so, local media superseded the importance of national electronic media in influencing minds of the voters. Results of the surveys conducted by local media were far more accurate and real than the national one. Surveys also shown that American people, who were abroad at far flung places, having no access to local

media, had not even basic information of representative of their districts. So this survey has explicitly shown the importance of local media in reference to electoral politics.

Why electoral systems matter: an analysis of their incentives and effects on key areas of governance is an article published by Alina Rocha Menocal under Overseas Development Institute (ODI). The writer is a research fellow at afore mentioned institute having expertise in challenges of governance and democratization. She opines that electoral system is of crucial importance because it not only translates electoral votes into legislature seats but also lays critical impacts upon policy making and governance. Electoral systems define the incentives which ought to be given to masses and in return benefits achieved by political parties. “Understanding electoral incentives are therefore important to understand how institutional rules of the game interact with stakeholders – on the demand as well as on the supply side.”¹ There is a good deal of research work going on nowadays on relationship between governance and nature of electoral system, particularly in the Third World. Literature gauges impact of electoral systems on party system and effectiveness of government. A good deal of literature is also focusing on link between electoral system and malpractices in neo democracies of the developing world.

This part of the research paper also explains how electoral system ca not be taken as a separate entity as it works in contingency with other institutional and structural factors. Nature of state system, form of government, religious, ethnic or linguistic status and demography are some variables which impact or even determine any electoral system.

Further in the research paper, the writer explains the typology of electoral systems and broadly categorized into three, i.e. Proportional Representation Systems, Plurality or Majority Systems and mixed systems. These broad division has further been divided into ‘sub-families’ in the paper. Then it is explained that what electoral system and why is suitable to conflict prone societies.

In the end, electoral malpractice has been explained beautifully. It is so because the explanation is very much relevant to the Third World in general and

Pakistan in particular. “Electoral Autocracies” have been established in the Third World since the wave of democratization of the world after the demise of communism. These electoral autocracies not only hampered the way of level playing field for every stake holder but also tilt the things in favor of incumbent government. So much so that certain organizations and groups become adept at maneuvering electoral politics in their favor to come in power time and again. Though the writer believes that with the incremental changes in the systems, things could be improved gradually.

Voting behavior in rural and urban areas of Punjab is a research paper written by Dr. Mughees Ahmad published in Journal of Political Studies in 2008. The writer is a Professor in Government College University Faisalabad. In this research article, he aims at studying behavior of voters in the Punjab. According to him, *Biradriism* is the key determinant of this behavior and it gives shape to political arrangements as well. Intermittent shocks to political system, martial laws and non party elections further corroborated biradri system in politics of Pakistan in general and Punjab in particular. Even elections of local bodies enhanced this trend as well. The writer has taken case study of Faisalabad district and convincingly explained how colonialism strengthened biradriism in Punjab. Right of vote was granted to people having private property; hence they monopolized the politic affairs of society which is continuing till the date. Cast system and demography in the district has been explained in detail. Behaviors of people are constituted by social class plus one or more than one variables like religion, ethnicity or urban-rural divide. Problem is faced when any state fails to maintain a balance between these variables and imposes one upon the other. In the end, the writer has done a historical comparison of role of biradris in politics of the Punjab and claims that it holds a central position in it.

Role Of Biradari System In Power politics Of Lahore Post Independence Period is a thesis of Political Science written by Muhammad Ibrahim. The writer believes that power politics in the Punjab in colonial, as well as post-colonial era has always been manipulated by biradri factor. Politics in Pakistan has always analyzed on macro factors like political parties, military, bureaucracy and international environment and very less attention has been paid to this important aspect. This study throws light the way colonial raj corroborated kinship system and how this system made its permanent configuration in politics of Pakistan in general and Lahore in particular. This system is so much entrenched in society of the

Punjab that it seems to be guarding its social anthropology. Lahore has undergone dramatic changes after the partition era. Before that, agriculture was the economic hub of this city. So naturally, agriculture was of prime concern to the politics of the city. But due to the development done under the colonial rule, Lahore was transformed in to an urban area till the time of independence. Due to this, there was an influx of population in this city to avail opportunities. Besides, partition of India disturbed its ethnic and demographic setup and gave a new dimension to biradri setup in the city. Since then, biradris have been playing a pivotal role in virtually all the political activities of Lahore. From a mini rural area, this city has become one of the largest and populated urban areas of the world.

System of caste has lost its importance talking in general in Lahore, but ironically, it is yet intact when it comes to electoral politics. It is so because the existing colonial structure protected the interests of biradris, so the same trend continued after the independence. Araen and Kashmiri biradris have been playing a dominant role in power structure of Lahore. The researcher has chapter wise discussed the emergence and monopoly of biradri system plainly. Besides, role of overseas Pakistanis have also been talked about in context of biradri politics.

Electoral Politics in NWFP 1988-1999 is a thesis of Pakistan Studies written by Muhammad Shakeel Ahmad. This research gives a detailed analysis of electoral politics in North West Frontier Province. Voting behavior is the prime variable studied in the research. The writer negates the common perception that social factors like party’s loyalty in urban areas and patronage in rural areas are too much important in electoral process of the province. The research studies the election results of the elections held from 1988-1999, i.e. 1988, 1990, 1993 and 1997. Findings are based upon primary as well as secondary sources. Quantitative and qualitative data regarding electoral data has extensively been studied. Focal point of the study is the factors that determine voting behavior of the voters and make them participate in democratic process. The writer tries to locate who is voting whom and why?

Research is based upon two assumptions, i.e., social factors are determinants of voting behavior and secondly, political determinants affect voting behavior of voters. To answer these research questions, a sociological, a psychosocial model and rational choice theory has been applied.

Democracy in Pakistan: Value Change and Challenges of Institution Building is a research article written by Dr. Saeed Shafqat, published in The Pakistan Development Review in 1998. Article starts with a brief introduction to democracy and certain values associated with it and explain the importance of electoral politics in translating opinion of people into reality. The writer believes that there have been very less pedagogical efforts to explain experiments of Pakistan with democracy. Most of the studies have focused on failure of process of democratization in the country but no one gave importance to theory of democracy and its implementation here. Pakistan is one of those few Third World countries which have shown great inclination towards democracy and mass movements against military dictatorship. Though ground realities of the country like ethnic composition, demography, geography and colonial hangover are big resistances on the way democratization; nevertheless, growth of political parties, increase in number of non-governmental organizations, human rights groups and inclusion of regional parties into mainstream are silver linings for the process of democratization. Era of 1990s was longest civilian government led era; though no government was made to complete its tenure, however, principles of democracy and electoral competition gained strength. But still much is needed to be done in order to strengthen democracy.

In order to analyze the relationship between transition of democracy and building political institutions; measuring forces which build or resist democracy and gauging role of leadership in democratic development in the country, this research paper works on four themes, i.e., Contesting election and supremacy of elected officials, electoral competition, behavior of political elite including their disability to perform in parliamentary democracy and “political parties and challenges of democratic development.”(Shafqat 1998)

The writer concludes with his findings that political leaders of the country are not committed with democratic principles. They don't concede parliament as prime forum of decision making. Secondly, due to political stability and continuity of political system, secessionist tendencies in the regional parties have eroded and they have entered into the mainstream. Resultantly, federation has got stronger. Thirdly, there is resentment in people about the dynastic nature of political parties. Fourthly, due to an international environment, chances of a direct military coup are minimal and lastly, there is mushroom growth in print media which has good omens for democratization.

Political Participation of the Educated in Pakistan is a research article published in Journal of Elementary Education, co authored by Ifra Mushtaq, Muhammad Abiodullah and Razaqat Ali Akber. This article examines the level of participation and behavior of the people in political system by studying their socio economic resource level (SERL). Democracies have always emerged from a particular democratic culture. This culture is invoked by proactive citizens who take keen interest and participate in political affairs.

This participation can both be conventional or unconventional. Education is one of the most important elements of conventional participation. Educated people are more vigilant towards ongoing political developments. Likewise, studies have shown that socio economic level is highly associated with political participation. People with high socio economic status are more sensitive towards governmental policies because they are highly affected by them. Likewise, people who consume more media and news channels are likable to fall in political talks easily and “talk leads to recruitment.” (Mushtaq, 2013) Theories depict that political talks have a reasonable impact upon political and civil participation.

The researchers opine that political attitude and behavior differ with the change in socio economic resource level. People having high SERL are very proactive in political participation as compared to the low. It is so because prior ones are ambitious to influence decision making process which lays profound affects on them. The researchers have testified three hypothesis, i.e. “H1: High SERL group tends to consume greater amount of political programs on news media as compared to the low and middle SERL groups. H2: High SERL group is more likely to engage in political conversations as compared to low and middle SERL groups. H3: High socio economic resource level (SERL) group of citizens are more likely to be involved in conventional modes of political participation as compared to low and middle SERL groups.” (Mushtaq,2013) Survey was conducted on 500 respondents across four cities of Pakistan. A scale was formed keeping in view the education and income level of families.

After having a quantitative analysis, the researchers found out that people having middle or low SERL are apathetic to politics. They are even unaware how politics affect their common day life. Conversely, group with high SERL were much more agile in

political conversations, consumed more media and politically mobilized.

Education and Democracy is a research article written by E. F. Provenzo and Thousand Oaks, published in Encyclopedia of Social and Cultural Foundations of Education. Writers opine that democracy has always been important in educating masses. Theorizers have always tried to figure out the educational necessity of maintaining and establishing democratic polity. Democracy and education, both, evolved in the United States evolved out of historic and geographic related concerns. Capitalism due to its dominant technologies, throughout the history, has set the limits, provided objectives and shaped policies and practices pertaining to public education. "Along with the cultural, social, and economic factors shaping contemporary public education, specific goals and their programmatic implications are intertwined in three partially overlapping forms of American democracy: Institutional Republicanism, Popular Democracy, and Deep Democracy." (Prevenzo and Aoas 2008) All the aforementioned types have certain common set of values. All the three advocate universal education and deem it pivotal for every citizen; however, each one of them defines education and democracy in their own way. These democratic forms have been co existing and competing with each other throughout 20th and 21st century, albeit public education provided by them has been uneven. Resultantly, shallow democracy has emerged in the United States. Voters become passive consumers of parties, policies and candidates.

A Dispassionate Analysis of How Elections are Stolen & Will of People is Defeated: Reflections on Electoral History of Pakistan (1970-2008) is a background paper published by Pakistan Institute of Legislative Development and Transparency in 2008. This paper was published before general election of 2008 and it aimed to analyze fairness and transparency of previous eight general elections. This paper has devised "Rigging Test" and tested general elections on criteria of pre poll, poll day post poll practices. Paper starts with certain questions like are elections free are fair in Pakistan? And will of people is translated through elections or are they stolen through rigging?

Rigging according to the paper published by PILDAT reflections of Electoral history in Pakistan 2008 are "all activities that violate the laws of Pakistan and constitutional provisions in holding of elections to determine the will of the people to form a government of their choice." Elections have been divided into high, low and medium level of rigging.

Pre poll rigging involves the attempts to dismantle the level playing field in favor of certain party. It is generally done through abusing caretaker government, Election Commission and even Judiciary. Voters' lists and polling station are also tampered in this stage. Polling day rigging is done through meddling with the integrity of vote, whether by altering ballots, wrong counting or tabulation or even thwarting voters to exercise the right of franchise. Post poll rigging includes use of unfair maneuvering to form government, generally against the public mandate.

Surveys have shown that confidence of people in fairness of the electoral process is very low despite of the willingness to vote. The paper verifies this assumption by testing all the general elections held in Pakistan from 1970 to 2002 on pre poll, poll day and post poll rigging criteria. Due to such a notorious record, when question was asked about the perception of people about fairness and transparency of upcoming 2008 elections, only 15 percent showed their confidence in the electoral process. The paper ends with the note that Pakistani democracy is a democracy sans rule of law. It was the reason that masses showed no reluctance whenever an elected government was sacked in 1990s because people seen the regimes as "governments minus rule of law."

The First Ten General Elections of Pakistan: A Story of Pakistan's Transition from Democracy Above Rule of Law to Democracy Under Rule of Law: 1970-2013 is a research paper published by Pakistan Institute of Legislative Development and Transparency in 2013. This paper makes a critical analysis of general elections of Pakistan. First general election of Pakistan was held in 1970 and since then electoral history of Pakistan has remained turbulent. Besides electoral, the country's societal and economic discourse has also been profoundly changed during the course of ten general elections. Structures of state have been going under a perpetual evolutionary process. This paper overlooks at the mutual relationship between political players, social changes and state institutions. These three have never been on the same page in political setup of Pakistan which signifies the troubled relationship.

The 1970 general election of Pakistan proved to be a nightmare for the state. It had swollen out of its existing size of political structures. Resultantly, country's social and geographic boundaries were altered. Second general elections of Pakistan were even more disastrous when institutional failure became even more evident. Political turmoil resulted

into forceful transfer of power from civilian to military regime. Succeeding seven elections have been analyzed in context of the changes they brought in socio economic profile of voting in the paper. Role of Inter Services Intelligence (ISI) and Military Intelligence (MI) has always been dominant in maneuvering electoral process particularly when transfer of power was from military to civil. However, things certainly improved from 2008 elections when military played the role of a facilitator. Next chapter of the research paper constitute detailed data analysis of general election results ever held in Pakistan.

On Democracy is an excerpt from Democracy and Educational Administration written by the famous writer John Dewey. The writer believes that democracy can not be just confined to some myopic concepts like exercising the right of franchise, law making or running government; rather it is a much broader term. All these concepts are related to democracy but it is much deeper and broader than that. These notions are just means to an end. End, according to the writer, lie in broader domain of human personality development and inter human relationships. Democracy ensures peaceful co existence of human being which is inevitable for development of human beings as well as general welfare. Recurring elections, responsibilities of leaders towards voters, universal suffrage and many other factors are means that can be said expedient for a realization that democracy is truly the human lifestyle. The philosophy that every that person who is affected by any social institution by any means should have a share in making decisions is very much in accordance with human nature, though this thing has been seen as active and passive side by many a scholar.

Democracy is a social contract in which many voluntarily accept subordination of the few. No coercion or physical occupation is involved in the process but a few powerful deciding the fate of the rest is a form of despotism. During this process, masses even become unaware of the powers they actually possess. Even in the countries which have continuous and established democracies, ethics and ideals of leadership are imposed from the above.

One of the most important strands of democracy is equality; though this equality is not in psychological terms rather political and legal one. "The very fact of natural and psychological inequality is all the more reason for establishment by law of equality of opportunity, since otherwise the former becomes a means of oppression of the less gifted." (Dewey,

1937) According to the writer, speaking broadly, all institutions are educational in nature in a sense that they work to form the dispositions, attitudes, disabilities and abilities. This principle is peculiarly for the school institutions. "For it is the main business of the family and the school to influence directly the formation and growth of attitudes and dispositions, emotional, intellectual and moral." (Dewey, 1937) The way this process is carried out, i.e. democratic or undemocratic way, becomes patent not only for education itself but also to societal democratic way of life.

Electoral Malpractices during the 2008 Elections in Pakistan is a relevant book written by Iffat Humayun Khan. This book starts with defining what electoral malpractice actually is and explains the tactics of pre-poll, polling day and post electoral malpractices. Then the writer moves on writing the history of electoral malpractices that has been taking place since the inception of Pakistan. The writer has comprehensively discussed each and every election of history of Pakistan and discussed even the minor details of electoral practices. The writer has beautifully connected the military-bureaucratic nexus which time n again became a tool of rigging as an institution.

Afzal's Pakistan: History and Politics 1947-1971 is an account of history and politics of Pakistan from its birth to the fall of East Pakistan. This book comprehensively describes the political decay of Pakistan since its inception and that is intricately connected to the establishment of Bangladesh. Electoral politics has been discussed in detail and intermittent shocks to political system leading to breakup of the state has discussed in detail. (Afzaal, 2011)

The book *Government and Politics in Pakistan* by Mushtaq Ahmad is an account of complexities of politics of Pakistan. The continuous tug of war of power between military and political elite led to destroy political system of Pakistan. Making and breaking of the constitution and imposition of martial laws is its subject matter; and how it adversely affected the democratic system of our state.

Renowned journalist Fareed Zakria wrote an article *The Rise of Illiberal Democracy* in Foreign Affairs magazine. This article can help well in understanding the Third World democracies. He begins this article by mentioning the rise of nationalist movements ongoing around the world. Though most of the countries in the world are democratic but still there is a mushroom growth of 'illiberal democracies.'

According to the writer, 'liberal democracies' are the one which not only have free, fair and transparent elections but also adherent to supplementary concepts of democracy like rule of law, protection of basic human rights, liberty of speech, right to assembly and freedom of religion and property. He calls this as 'constitutional liberalism.' (Zakaria, 2003) Conversely, in illiberal democracies, democracy is adopted as a system of government but its supplementary concepts are rarely conferred to people. The writer also differentiates between 'democracy' and 'constitutional liberalism.'

Pakistan: A Modern History is a famous book on historical and political developments of Pakistan. Ian Talbot is its writer. In this book, Ian Talbot has discussed the reasons for why Pakistan has not been turned into a successful nation state. According to the writer, non-continuity of democratic system and authoritarian system proved to be the biggest stumbling block in development of Pakistan. Besides, cultural diversity of the country has always been seen as a threat by authoritarian regimes. Socio-economic culture of the country since the time of birth of the state helped the elite to make political parties and come at helm of affairs. Hence leadership demagoguery and personality cult became the order of the day of political parties. The writer has also done a critical analysis of important political leaders from Zulfikar Ali Bhutto to Nawaz Sharif.

Michael Gallagher and Paul Mitchell have written the book titled *The Politics of Electoral System*. In this book, the writers have initially described the importance of electoral system as it is a link which connects demands of the people to the political elite or the policy makers. Then the writers have done a comparative analysis of political systems of the world; followed by the detailed description of how electoral system works in twenty two countries, eleven of the Western Europe and eleven from rest of the world. This book is a good account of how electoral system in any country were historically chosen; what is the current mechanism of operating of the electoral system; and what are the political consequences of the existing electoral system. This book is worth reading if one has to study the comparative analysis of developed and developing electoral systems.

Education, Democracy and Moral Life is another relevant book authored by Michael S. Katz, Susan Verducci and Gert Biesta. This book seeks the mutual connection of education, democracy and the moral life. The authors have discussed the critical role of

education in producing democratic citizens who must be socially responsible as well.

Besides, inculcation of democratic patriotism through education; relationship between inclusion and exclusion in democratic education; role of internet blogs in advancing democratic learning and grooming moral sensibility in citizens are some other unique issues which have been explored in the book. (Verdusi and Biesta 2008)

Role Of Biradari System In Power politics Of Lahore Post Independence Period is a thesis of Political Science written by Muhammad Ibrahim. The writer believes that power politics in the Punjab in colonial, as well as post-colonial era has always been manipulated by biradri factor. Politics in Pakistan has always analyzed on macro factors like political parties, military, bureaucracy and international environment and very less attention has been paid to this important aspect. This study throws light the way colonial raj corroborated kinship system and how this system made its permanent configuration in politics of Pakistan in general and Lahore in particular. This system is so much entrenched in society of the Punjab that it seems to be guarding its social anthropology. Lahore has undergone dramatic changes after the partition era. Before that, agriculture was the economic hub of this city. So naturally, agriculture was of prime concern to the politics of the city. But due to the development done under the colonial rule, Lahore was transformed in to an urban area till the time of independence. Due to this, there was an influx of population in this city to avail opportunities. Besides, partition of India disturbed its ethnic and demographic setup and gave a new dimension to biradri setup in the city. Since then, biradris have been playing a pivotal role in virtually all the political activities of Lahore. From a mini rural area, this city has become one of the largest and populated urban areas of the world.

System of caste has lost its importance talking in general in Lahore, but ironically, it is yet intact when it comes to electoral politics. It is so because the existing colonial structure protected the interests of biradris, so the same trend continued after the independence. Araen and Kashmiri biradris have been playing a dominant role in power structure of Lahore. The researcher has chapter wise discussed the emergence and monopoly of biradri system plainly. Besides, role of overseas Pakistanis have also been talked about in context of biradri politics.

Electoral Politics in NWFP 1988-1999 is a thesis of Pakistan Studies written by Muhammad Shakeel

Ahmad. This research gives a detailed analysis of electoral politics in North West Frontier Province. Voting behavior is the prime variable studied in the research. The writer negates the common perception that social factors like party's loyalty in urban areas and patronage in rural areas are too much important in electoral process of the province. The research studies the election results of the elections held from 1988-1999, i.e. 1988, 1990, 1993 and 1997. Findings are based upon primary as well as secondary sources. Quantitative and qualitative data regarding electoral data has extensively been studied. Focal point of the study is the factors that determine voting behavior of the voters and make them participate in democratic process. The writer tries to locate who is voting whom and why?

Research is based upon two assumptions, i.e., social factors are determinants of voting behavior and secondly, political determinants affect voting behavior of voters. To answer these research questions, a sociological, a psychosocial model and rational choice theory has been applied.

CONCLUSION:

I have concluded from my whole research that factors that facilitate social environment and health are varied. And they directly or indirectly affect the electoral processes in Pakistan. The effect of voting and political decisions touch nearly every faced of daily life from safety to housing, to education and even our health and other medical related issues. The relationship between health, education and voting is both well evaluated in this research and are reciprocal. Research shows that healthier you are and well educated the more likely you are to cast a ballot. This research also shows that voting can actually makes people healthier. Social connections are really important for physical health and education because social capital relates to an underline ideal that can determine the health and educational states and in turn our voting system as we have to decide where we are going as a country morally, economically and politically.

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